

An Example of Use of Usa-DSL Process: Supplemental Materials

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1 Context

In order to understand the behavior of the Usa-DSL Process we performed an simple example of use applying a Usability Method Heuristic Evaluation to evaluate a Textual DSL. To perform the example of use we chose to evaluate the LaTeX language, since it is a widely-used language in the academia. Therefore, this document presents the details of the example of use made, the description of the DSL used, the Guide for using Latex in the Overleaf environment and the tasks to be performed. Besides, the documentation used to conduct the evaluation was also presented, the informed consent form, the profile questionnaire and the applied checklist.

1.1 DSL for Typesetting System

LATEX is a document preparation system with a formal and professional appearance. When using it, the user types text in a simple way, instead of text using formatting such as Microsoft Word, Libre Office Writer and Apple Pages. This system is based on WYSIWYG (“What You See Is What You Get”) word processors, it identifies web or text editors that show the user the final result of what he is editing in real time.

Another important point of Latex is that users use tagging conventions to define the general structure of the document (for instance article, book or letter), to format the text in your document (such as bold, italic and underline), to add citations and cross-references, including tables and figures among other features. The use of these tagging means that the user when using Latex focuses on the content and the computer will take care of the formatting of your document.

We use the Overleaf to facilitate the use of Latex, which is a web-based, online, and collaborative tool. This tool aims to make the process of writing, editing and publishing scientific documents faster and easier. This tool has two windows side by side, in one of its windows the tool presents the code and in the other window the view of the result of its writing, that is, its editing takes place directly in the document code, generating a PDF view of the written code. Overleaf also has a library with different templates from different institutions that can be used. Further, the environment provides a repository to upload figures or other document types that could be used into the document. Furthermore, the Overleaf is able to share the document with other collaborators, who could be editing remotely and simultaneously the same document.

2 Usa-DSL Process Instance

For this usability evaluation, we use the combination of the heuristic evaluation method with the empirical survey method. Usa-DSL first aided us in the development of the Evaluation Protocol, in which all activities and tasks that must be performed for this step followed. We generate all documents from the examples presented in the description of each activity following the steps that are guided by the tasks. For this example of use, we perform the Heuristic Evaluation process, which will be described next, according to the flow shown in Figure 1.

2.1 Planning

The Planning phase were executed the following activities and tasks:

Figure 1: An Example Usa-DSL Process

- P5 - Define Evaluation Usability Type: in this activity we define the Heuristic Evaluation method among the options available in the tasks.
- P6 - Define Empirical Evaluation Method: by process definition, we use the Survey method, which is predefined when the Heuristic Evaluation method is selected.
- P1 - Define Evaluator Profile: the heuristic evaluation subjects must be HCI expert for this evaluation type selected. These participants aim to evaluate the DSL and contribute to the group of developers from the errors and degree of severity pointed out during the evaluation, seeking to improve usability and user experience before presenting the DSL to end users.
- P2 - Define Informed Consent Term: In this task, we defined a consent term. This document can be seen in Appendix A.
- P7- Define the Instruments of Data Gathering: This task was performed by select the instrument that is used to collect the participant's opinion regarding the DSL evaluated. The instruments selected from the elected Usability Evaluation are Heuristic Evaluation Checklist and Profile Questionnaire.
- P3 - Define Data Type: In this activity, we chose the qualitative data because it is composed of subjective information related to the participant's opinion about the studied object.
- P8 - Define Instruments of Instructions and Training: At this moment we described the DSL in the Language presentation, defined the used scenario, and constructed the DSL guide (where explained the DSL evaluated).
- P9 - Define Execution Place: For this study, we invited the participants and send the Instruments of Instructions and Training by e-mail because we live a pandemic moment (COVID-19).

- P10 - Define Data Storage: The documents and the results have been stored in the Google Drive.
- P11 - Define Study Reporting: The study will be reported in a scientific article.

2.2 Execution

- E4 - Develop and Conduct Protocol: The developing of the evaluation was consists by description all the steps that will be used, among that the background, type of the usability evaluation, experimental study, context, objectives, profile of the participants, the instruments, data storage and how the study will be reported. This consist in all sections and subsections of this document.
- E5 - Prepare the Evaluation: During this activity we organize the instruments defined in the activities P2, P7 P8, P9 and P10. In this activity, the availability of the participants was confirmed, that is, the date that could perform the evaluation was confirmed. After defining the date and sending the prepared documentation, another e-mail was sent confirming the receipt of the questions, because the whole evaluation process was conducted online.
- E1 - Apply Instruments to Identify Profiles: The instrument was send by Google forms, this document can be seen in Appendix B.1

- E2 - Introduce the Form and Collect the Signature of Subjects: The instrument was explained by an e-mail and in the introduction in the Google forms.

- E8 - Introduce Instruments of Instruction and Conduct Training: during this activity, we present a guide that orients which DSL will be evaluated, as well as it is functioning its syntax and semantics. Still in this activity, we present the DSL links to be evaluated and how the participant should proceed to access it. [This activity is composed by two tasks - E8a and E8b - that will be detailed as follows.](#)

E8a - Deliver the DSL Guide: *Guide for Latex DSL* - To participate in this research it will be necessary for the participant to explore a Textual DSL. This DSL uses the Overleaf online environment to write a scientific paper in the ACM template using the Latex language. To explore this DSL the participant must access the Link to login: <https://v2.overleaf.com/login> and access the shared file <https://www.overleaf.com/6347991679hgnttggykqh>. If you do not have an Overleaf account you must first create your account. After logging into the environment, you should open the file for some tasks that will help explore the representation and functioning of the language.

E8b - Deliver the Use Scenario: **Textual DSL Tasks:** Here, we enumerate the tasks that should be executed by the participant:

1. Delete a command “\textbf”. Click on the “Compile” button. Observe the action;
2. Undo the previous action. Click on the “Compile” button. Observe the action;
3. Add a picture. Observe the action;
4. Click on the “Compile” button. Observe the output in the PDF;
5. Add an “Item List”. Click on the “Compile” button. Observe the output in the PDF;
6. Delete a “Paragraph”. Click on the “Compile” button. Observe the output in the PDF;
7. Observe the icon showing the number of errors;
8. Check the list of errors in the code.

- E9 - Execution of Tasks and Evaluation Conduct: [This activity is composed by two tasks - E9a and E9b - that will be detailed as follows.](#)

E9a - Perform Modeling of the use Scenario: In this task the participant model the instructions defined in task E8b - Deliver the Use Scenario.

E9d - Complete the Heuristic Evaluation Checklist: In this task, the participant was complete the checklist. The answers can be seen in Appendix C.

- E7- Data Collection: The data were all collected online, through informed consent term, profile questionnaires and Heuristic Evaluation Checklist. These documents can be seen in Appendix A, B.1, C.
- E10 - Store Data Obtained: The data obtained was stores in a research account on Google Drive.

2.3 Analysis

- A4 - Analyze the Developed Protocol: The protocol was reviewed for the Process Executor and other researchers, and what was not in accordance with the desired was corrected in the final protocol.
- A1 - Analyze Evaluator Profiles: The evaluator profile was analyzed in the final study. We verified the experience of the participants which usability and heuristic evaluation, time of experience using or designing DSL (in years), as well as time of experience using or designing DSL, among others (Can be seen at Table 1.
- A7 - Analyze the Collected Data: The coding of the data obtained in the evaluation was realized so that the analysis can be realized. After coding, the inference of the results of the study was realized and show in R7 - Report Data Analysis.
- A11 - Analyze the Documentation: The documentation was analyzed for two experts, both are Ph.D. lecturers and researchers, and have two and nine years of experience on designing DSLs, respectively.

2.4 Reporting

- R5 - Report Conduct Evaluation: For this evaluation, we used the Heuristic Evaluation for the Usability Method. That protocol includes the specific artifact the Heuristic Evaluation Checklist and use the survey protocol for reporting each planned, executed and analyzed step.
- R4 - Report the Developed Protocol: The Heuristic Evaluation has as defined empirical evaluation method, the Survey protocol. This protocol follows the Guideline (Artifact: Survey Protocol) presented on the website of the Usa-DSL Process, <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1DyWsoGDtHJkr3UBgxbq-2grLjfFZeP/view?usp=sharing>.
- R1 - Report Evaluator Profiles: The analysis of the participant profiles point out that one is undergrad students and four are master students. Thus, the average time of experience using or designing DSL is 2.4 years. Some participants have experience time in performing or participating in usability evaluation, where three participants have just one year of experience. Besides, two of them have already participated of usability evaluation using usability testing, meanwhile two other of them have have already participated of usability evaluation using heuristic evaluation. Furthermore, just one of the participants have already conducted a usability evaluation using heuristic evaluation.
- R2 - Report Subjects Number and Form Used: The subject number is five (5) participants and the form used was Profile Questionnaire B.1.
- R8 - Report the Instruments: The instruments used was Informed Consent Term A, Profile Questionnaire B.1, DSL guide and Heuristic Evaluation Checklist for DSL Textual.
- R9 - Report Tasks Analysis: The tasks that were analyzed are the commands executed in the latex file sent to the participants. These tasks were executed according to the description sent together with the DSL Explanation Guide.
- R7 - Report Data Analysis: The analysis of the results of the Heuristic Evaluation Checklist points to the following analysis for each heuristic:

H1 Q1: The experts E1 and E2 describes that “The compile does not shows where the modifications have being performed”. Besides, the DSL does not present a commit message for each change, but is able to report in real time if there is a minor error (*e.g.* the lack of keys), before compiling.

As for the severity degree, both agree that it is 1, a cosmetic problem only, however E4, considers the severity degree 2, *i.e.* a low priority.

H2 Q2: Experts (E2, E3 and E5) agree that there is no undo button and mention that the action is only possible using the Ctrl + Z keys. With regard to severity degree, two of the experts to this problem attributed degree 2, *i.e.* fixing this should be given low priority.

H3 Q3: Expert E5 relates that Latex has abbreviated keywords/statements, and that this makes it difficult for other users to adopt this language. He also reports that the severity degree of this problem is 3, *i.e.* important to fix, so should be given high priority.

H4 Q6: Expert E3 reports that some errors are shown in real time and others are required to be compiled to be presented. It also indicates that the Latex does not provide information about commit, and this may be part of the tool that instantiates the language. With regard to severity degree for this problem, the degree attributed was 1 being this a cosmetic problem only.

H5 Q7: Regarding H3, the experts E1, E2, E3 and E5 report that there are synchronization problems, the environment warns that changes are made in a certain period of time and that they may not have been saved. Furthermore, they still state that the changes are saved automatically, but if there is a drop in the Internet service, the reconnection notice displayed may not be accurate and the changes in the document are not saved. E1 says: "The problems are only showed after the .tex compilation". This question presents disagreement of the severity degree among participants, who pointed out the following degrees 1, 2 and 4. Hence, it is not consensus among them related to this question.

H6 No problem found.

H7 Q11: Experts (E1, E4 and E5) explain that the environment does not have confirmation boxes or buttons for actions, however for image writing there is confirmation when compiling. On the one hand, E1 assigns severity degree 2 because it must be modified with a low degree of priority. On the other hand, E4 and E5 assign severity degree 1, so it should only be fixed if the project has available time.

H8 No problem found.

H9 Q16: Expert E2 replies that if you consider the generated pdf by Latex as an output, in this case the changes do occur. On the other hand, E4 states that there is no graphic DSL, only the preview of the text written in the generated pdf. Besides, E5 considers that only when the changes to the textual DSL are compiled are observed in the graphical DSL. The severity degree assigned is zero, so they do not consider a usability problem.

H10 Q19: Experts (E2 and E3) specify that to have a color change, commands specific to latex must be entered, in other cases they are just text. These experts consider that this is not a usability problem and attribute a zero severity level.

H11 Q20: Experts (E2, E3 and E4) state that the error messages are not intuitive or easy to understand, on the contrary they are confusing and hinder rather than help. Such messages are difficult to be identified quickly and to verify which error is presenting, albeit it is often necessary a much more technical knowledge to deal with errors. Furthermore, E2 assigns a severity degree and needs to be repaired with a high priority, E3 and E4 assign a degree 2 claim that it must be fixed but with a low priority.

H12 Q21: Experts (E1, E2 and E5) mention that there is no tutorial for Latex, however the templates have it. Also, E3 states that there are documentation and books that help the use of Latex. Moreover, related to the severity degree attributed by those who say there is no documentation ranges from cosmetics to usability catastrophe.

- R11 - Report the Results and Analyzed Information: To present the results of the study, a scientific article was chosen in addition to this supplementary material.

A Informed Consent Term

Usa-DSL Process: Heuristic Evaluation Checklist

Heuristic Evaluation Checklist - Usa-DSL

You are being invited to participate in the research " Usa-DSL Process - Heuristic Evaluation Checklist", under the responsibility of the Ph.D. student XX, under the guidance of Professor XX

You will participate in a Survey in which you must perform a task and identify the problems found in DSL Latex. During this inspection, you must fill in the Heuristic Evaluation Checklist-Usa-DSL.

The information obtained through this research will be confidential and we will ensure the confidentiality of your participation. Thus, the disclosed data will not allow any identification.

Even without having direct benefits in participating, indirectly you will be contributing to the understanding of the phenomenon studied and to the production of scientific knowledge.

This evaluation is composed of three main sections: the first section for Respondent Identification, the second Guide for Latex DSL and task the final section Heuristic Evaluation Checklist.

Your participation in this study will require approximately 20 - 30 minutes.

Any questions regarding the research can be made through the researchers' emails: XX

*Obrigatório

1. STATEMENT OF CONSENT OF THE SUBJECT OF THE RESEARCH I agree to participate in this study and I declare that I have read the details described in this document. I understand that I am free to accept or refuse, and that I can interrupt my participation at any time without giving a reason why. I agree that the data collected will be used for the purpose described above. I understand the information presented in this CONSENT TERMS. I had the opportunity to ask questions and all my questions were answered. I will receive a signed and dated copy of this FREE AND CLARIFIED CONSENT Document. *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

Agree

B Profile Questionnaire

This section present the profile questionnaire document and data profile collected. The data profile is described in Table 1.

B.1 HCI Experts Profile Data

Table 1: Data Profile

HCI Expert	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6
E1	Omitted	Master Student	1	0	Usability	None
E2	Omitted	Master Student	5	1	Heuristic	None
E3	Omitted	Master Student	3	0	None	None
E4	Omitted	Master Student	1	1	Usability	None
E5	Omitted	Undergrad Student	2	1	Heuristic	Heuristic

Profiles Questions (Table 1):

- Q1 - Name of institution or company.
- Q2 - What is your work position?
- Q3 - Time of experience using or designing DSL (in years).
- Q4 - Time of experience in performing or participating in Usability Evaluation (in years).
- Q5 - Check the usability evaluation method(s) that you have already participated.
- Q6 - Check the usability evaluation method(s) that you have already conducted.

B.2 Template Profile Questionnaire

Profile Questionnaire

2. Name and Surname *

3. e-mail *

4. Name of Institution or Company *

5. What is your work position? *

6. Time of experience using or designing DSL (in years) *

7. Time of experience in performing or participating in Usability Evaluation (in years) *

8. Check the usability evaluation method(s) that you have already participated *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Heuristic Evaluation

Usability Testing

None

9. Check the usability evaluation method(s) that you have already conducted: *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Heuristic Evaluation
- Usability Testing
- None

Guide
for
Latex
DSL
and
Task

To participate in this research it will be necessary for the participant to explore a Textual DSL. Textual DSL uses the Overleaf online environment to write a scientific paper in the ACM template using the Latex language.

To explore this DSL the participant must access the Link to login: <https://v2.overleaf.com/login> and access the shared file <https://www.overleaf.com/6347991679hgnttggykqjh>.

If you do not have an Overleaf account you must first create your account. After logging into the environment, you should open the file for some tasks that will help explore the representation and functioning of the language.

Tasks DSL Textual

- 1 - Delete a command "textbf". Click on the "Compile" button. Observe the action;
- 2 - Undo the previous action. Click on the "Compile" button. Observe the action;
- 3 - Add a picture. Observe the action;
- 4 - Click on the "Compile" button. Observe the output in the PDF;
- 4 - Add an "Item List". Click on the "Compile" button. Observe the output on PDF;
- 5 - Delete a "Paragraph". Click on the "Compile" button. Observe the output in the PDF;
- 6 - Observe the icon showing the number of errors;
- 7 - Check the list of errors in the code.

Heuristic
Evaluation
Checklist -
Usa-DSL

After exploring the textual DSL, the participant must complete the Heuristic Evaluation Checklist for Textual DSL. The Checklist must be accessed via the link https://drive.google.com/file/d/1loeGwBZY_oxWIsKLwY9geLD4KpoXaFni/view?usp=sharing.

Thank you for your time and opinion.

Este conteúdo não foi criado nem aprovado pelo Google.

Google Formulários

C Heuristic Checklist

C.1 Results of the Heuristic Evaluation Checklists

Results of the Heuristic Evaluation Checklist																	
Heuristic	Question	Apply or Not Apply					Severity					Describe Problem E1	Describe Problem E2	Describe Problem E3	Describe Problem E4	Describe Problem E5	Result Analysis
		E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5						
H1	Q1		NA	NA	A	A	1	1		2	0	The compile does not shows where the modifications have being performed.	Não existe mensagem de commit de cada mudança, mas a DSL consegue informar em tempo real caso haja um erro menor (faltando um sinal de chaves por exemplo), antes de compilar.				Os Experts E1 e E2 descrevem que a ação compilar não mostra a linha que foi modificada "The compile does not shows where the modifications have being performed". E que a DSL não apresenta mensagem de commit a cada mudança, porém consegue informar em tempo real caso haja um erro menor (por exemplo a falta de chaves), antes de compilar. Quanto ao grau de severidade 1 os dois concordam que é um Cosmetic problem only, porém o E4 apesar de não especificar o problema considera o grau de severidade 2 ou seja de prioridade baixa.
	Q2		NA	A	A	NA	0	2	0		2		Não existe necessariamente um botão para desfazer a ação realizada, isso é possível apenas através do menu de contexto do mouse ou das teclas de atalho ctrl+z	O ctrl+z é um atalho especificado pela ferramenta, não sei se isto se aplica a DSL em si		Don't exists undo button	Os Experts E2, E3 e E5 concordam que não existe botão de desfazer e mencionam que a ação só é possível ser realizada através das teclas ctrl+z. O grau de severidade atribuído por dois dos experts para este problema foi 2, ou seja fixing this should be given low priority.
H2	Q3		A	NA	A	A	1				3					The keywords presented in DSL are abbreviated. And difficult for other users to adopt.	O Expert E5 relata que a DSL apresenta palavras-chave abreviadas, e que isso torna difícil a adoção desta DSL por outros usuários. Ele ainda reporta que o grau de severidade deste problema é 3 "important to fix, so should be given high priority".
	Q4		A	NA	A	A	0				0						Não foi encontrado problemas
	Q5		A	NA	A	A	0				0						Não foi encontrado problemas
H3	Q6		A	A	A	A	0		1		0			Alguns erros são mostrados em tempo real, outros precisam do "compile" para aparecer. Em relação a committe a DSL não provem nenhuma informação, talvez isto seja parte da tool que instancia a linguagem.			O Expert E3 reporta que alguns erros são mostrados em tempo real e outros é necessária a compilação para serem apresentados. Ainda indica que a DSL não prove informações sobre commit, e isso pode ser parte da ferramenta que instancia a linguagem. O grau de severidade atribuído para este problema é 1 sendo este um Cosmetic problem only.
	Q7		NA	NA	A	A	1	4			2	The problems are only showed after the .tex compilation	No caso do exemplo não há aviso nenhum pois como é uma plataforma web, ocorre o salvamento automático. Contudo se há queda de internet o aviso de reconexão exibido pode não ser muito preciso. Falo isso pois já ocorreu de trabalhar em documento .tex nessa plataforma sem nenhum feedback de que a conexão havia caído (ou avisando que as mudanças realizadas offline poderiam ser perdidas). No momento em que ocorria a conexão todo o trabalho desenvolvido no período sem internet era perdido e o documento atualizado para a última "versão online"	Se há problemas de sincronização a ferramenta avisa que mudanças realizadas em um determinado espaço de tempo podem não terem sido salvas.	Can you insert an error and do not know. An example is 'dsaodjsoa[sample].	Referente H3, 4 Experts E1, E2, E3 e E5 reportam que há problemas de sincronização a plataforma avisa que são realizadas mudanças em um determinado espaço de tempo e que podem não terem sido salvas. Ainda afirmam que as alterações são salvas automaticamente, mas se há queda de internet o aviso de reconexão exibido pode não ser preciso e as alterações no texto não são salvas. O E1 "The problems are only showed after the .tex compilation". O grau de severidade entre os participantes são 1, 2 e 4, ou seja o E1 acha que o problema é cosmético, o E2 catastrophe imperative to fix this before product can be released e E5 outro acha mportant to fix, so should be given high priority.	
H4	Q8		A	A	A	A	0				0						Não foi encontrado problema
	Q9		A	A	A	A	0				0						Não foi encontrado problema
	Q10	NA	A	A	A	A					0						Não foi encontrado problema

H5	Q11		A	A	NA	NA	2				1	1	The DSL allows users to perform these actions without showing confirmation boxes.		Apresenta em alguns casos específicos, como quando vai mudar uma imagem por outra. Mas não é muito grave, pois não existem muitas ações perigosas na DSL.	Apresenta apenas em alguns casos (sobrescrita de imagens).	Os Experts E1, E4 e E5 explicam que a DSL não apresenta caixas ou botões de confirmação para as ações, porém para sobre escrita de imagem existe a confirmação quando compila. O E1 atribui grau de severidade 2 pois deve ser modificado com baixo grau de prioridade. Já o E4 e E5 atribuem grau de severidade 1 então só deve ser arrumado caso tenha o projeto tenha tempo livre.
H6	Q12		A	A	A	A	0					0					Não foi encontrado problema
	Q13		A	A	A	A	0					0					Não foi encontrado problema
H7	Q14		A	A	A	A	0					0					Não foi encontrado problema
	Q15		A	A	A	A	0					0					Não foi encontrado problema
H7	Q16		NA	A	NA	NA	0	0				0	Se considerar a DSL gráfica como a saída em PDF gerada pelo LaTeX, as mudanças ocorrem de fato. Contudo, às vezes pode não ser tão fácil percebê-las (principalmente as mudanças pequenas) em documentos maiores. Contudo é possível contornar isso até certo ponto com a função de histórico presente no menu superior direito.	Comandos precisam de outros comandos específicos, para então serem identificados como comandos, se não são apenas texto.	Não existe uma DSL gráfica, apenas uma previsão de como o pdf gerado vai ficar.	Apenas após a ação "compilar"	O Expert E2 responde que se considerar o pdf gerada pelo Latex como saída, neste caso as mudanças ocorrem de fato. Já o E4 afirma que não existe uma DSL gráfica apenas a previsão do texto escrito no pdf gerado. E o E5 considera que somente quando é compilado as mudanças da DSL Textual são observadas na DSL Gráfica. O grau de Severidade atribuído é zero, portanto eles não consideram um problema de usabilidade.
H8	Q17		A	A	A	A	0					0					Não foi encontrado problema
	Q18	NA	A	A	A	A						0	0				Não foi encontrado problema
H8	Q19		NA	A	A	A	0	0				0	No exemplo específico dado (comando if/else) não há diferença nas cores dos comandos quando é escrito alguma forma de algoritmo no .tex	Comandos precisam de outros comandos específicos, para então serem identificados como comandos, se não são apenas texto.			E2 e E3 especificam que para haver mudança de cor devem ser digitados comandos específicos do latex, em outros casos são apenas texto. Eles consideram que isso não pe um problema de Usabilidade e atribuem grau de severidade zero.
H9	Q20		NA	NA	NA	A	0	3	2	2	2	0	Não é sempre que as mensagens de erro são intuitiva ou fáceis de compreender. Muitas vezes é necessário inclusive um conhecimento muito mais técnico.	As mensagens de erro podem ser confusas as vezes, atrapalhando, ao invés de auxiliar.	Alguns erros estão misturados com códigos, o que faz com que seja difícil identificar rapidamente com qual erro estamos lidando.		E2, E3 e E4 afirmam que as mensagens de erro não são intuitivas ou fáceis de compreender, pelo contrário são confusas e atrapalham invés de auxiliar. Tais mensagens são difíceis de sere identificadas rapidamente e verificar qual erro está apresentando, muitas vezes é necessário um conhecimento mais técnico para trata os erros. O E2 atribui grau de severidade e necessita ser consertado i com alta prioridade, o E3 e E4 atribuem grau 2 afirmam que deve ser consertado mas com grau de prioridade baixo.
H10	Q21		NA	A	A	A	1	3	0			1	The DSL itself does not have, however the templates have.	Não tem tutorial nativo que ensine o básico durante a primeira utilização,	No site do projeto latex existe toda a documentação e livros para auxiliar.	I don't know a tutorial of the LaTeX in overleaf.	E1, E2 e E5 mencionam que não existe tutorial para latex, porém os templates possuem. Já os E3 afirma que existe documentação e livros que auxiliam a utilização do Latex. O grau de severidade atribuído pelos que dizem não haver documentação vai de Cosmetico até alto grau de prioridade.
	Q22		A	NA	A	A	0					0					Não foi encontrado problema

Heuristic Evaluation Checklist for Textual DSL

This checklist is designed to be used together with the Process. The Nielsen Heuristics are used in the Heuristic Evaluation Checklist.

The following 0 to 4 rating scale can be used to rate the severity of usability problems:

Severity	Type	Description
0	Not applicable	I don't agree that this is a usability problem at all
1	Cosmetic problem only	need not be fixed unless extra time is available on project
2	Minor usability problem	fixing this should be given low priority
3	Major usability problem	important to fix, so should be given high priority
4	Usability catastrophe	imperative to fix this before product can be released

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Heuristic	Description	Question	Apply	Not apply	Description of each error occurrence	Severity (Check each of the problems found)				
						0	1	2	3	4
H1: Visibility of system status	The DSL should always keep users informed about what is going on, through appropriate feedback within reasonable time.	Does the Textual DSL provide immediate and adequate feedback on its status for each user action? For example, after an include or exclude task the language displays a commit message?		x						
		Do the elements available for the user specifically execute only one command? For example, the "undo" button only performs undo actions.	x		O ctrl+z é um atalho especificado pela ferramenta, não sei se isto se aplica a DSL em si	x				

H2: Match between language and the real world domain	The DSL must represent the user's language with words, phrases, and concepts familiar to the user instead of system-oriented. It should follow the conventions of the real world, making the information natural and logical.	Are the reserved keywords that compose the Textual DSL used on the user's real world domain? For example, a DSL developed for a domain related to libraries needs to have keywords related to the library domain.		x						
		Are the elements that compose the Textual DSL a good representation of the DSL's domain?		x						
		Do the elements that compose the Textual DSL meet the domain goal? The user understands the DSL goal by interacting with its elements.		x						
H3: User control and freedom	Users often choose DSL functions by mistake and will need a clearly marked "emergency exit" to leave the unwanted state without having to go through an extended dialogue. Support undo and redo.	Does the Textual DSL provide a mechanism in order to inform the restrictions of usage in case of, for example, mistyping or committing any kind of mistake?	x		Alguns erros são mostrados em tempo real, outros precisam do "compile" para aparecer. Em relação a committe a DSL não provem nenhuma informação, talvez isto seja parte da tool que instancia a linguagem.		x			
		Does the Textual DSL predict wrong decisions made by the users and warn them? For example, when the user clicks on a button for closing all the application and the tasks made by the user were not saved, does the Textual DSL warn the user that the application will be closed and nothing will be saved?		x	Se há problemas de sincronização a ferramenta avisa que mudanças realizadas em um determinado espaço de tempo podem não terem sido salvas.					
H4: Consistency and standards	Users should not have to wonder whether different words, situations, or actions mean the same thing.	Are all the Textual elements apparently connected to each other? For example, are all the reserved keywords shown in the same color?	X							
		Are all the Textual elements connected to each other according to	X							

		their names? For example, are all the reserved keywords written in the same style, only using camelCase or only using underscores (_) to separate words?								
		In case of using abbreviations, are all the abbreviations consistent throughout the DSL usage?	X							
H5: Error prevention	Even better than good error messages is a careful design which prevents a problem from occurring in the first place. Either eliminate error-prone conditions or check for them and present users with a confirmation option before they commit to the action.(confirmation box)	Does the Textual DSL show confirmation boxes when the user performs actions considered dangerous (deleting things, etc)?	X							
H6: Recognition rather than recall	Minimize the user's memory load by making objects, actions, and options visible. The user should not have to remember information from one part of the system to another. Instructions for use of the system	Do reserved keywords have a meaningful and easy name so that the user can remember them in a fast way? In this case, keywords are words related to the domain of the textual DSL.	X							
		Are commons tasks easy and fast to be executed? For example, opening a file or deleting an element.	X							

	should be visible or easily retrievable whenever appropriate.									
H7: Flexibility and efficiency of use	Accelerators — unseen by the novice user — may often speed up the interaction for the expert user such that the language can cater to both inexperienced and experienced users. Allow users to tailor frequent actions.	Does the Textual DSL have shortcuts for expert users to make the usage of the DSL in a fast way? For example, providing short-cuts or functions to write basic code structures.	X							
		Does the Textual DSL provide all the elements in order to complete the desired task?	X							
		Are the Textual and Graphical DSLs structured in a coupled way? For example, if the user changes something on the Textual DSL, this change must be observed on the Graphical DSL and if the user changes something on the Visual DSL, this change must be observed on the Textual DSL.	x							
H8: Aesthetic and minimalist design	Dialogues should not contain information that is irrelevant or rarely needed. Every extra unit of information in a dialogue competes with the relevant units of information and diminishes their relative visibility.	In case of showing a dialog (when the user commits a mistake, for example), does this dialog show the possible reasons why the mistake was committed in a clear way?	X							
		In case of showing a dialog, does this dialog have the information shown in a short-text? The quantity of lines of a short text may vary according to the dialog and the information being exposed, but it is advised that a dialog does not have more than 3 lines of warning.	X							
		Is the Textual DSL composed by	x		Comandos precisam de outros comandos					

		words easy to be seen on the screen (with good-contrast color, easily identified by the end user)? For example, commands like "if/else" are shown in a different color from the rest of the code.			específicos, para então serem identificados como comandos, se não são apenas texto.					
H9: Help users recognize, and diagnose, and recover from errors	Error messages should be expressed in plain language (no codes), precisely indicate the problem, and constructively suggest a solution.	In case of error, does the DSL show an appropriate error message where the user, after reading it, knows how to recover from the error or where to look for a solution?		X	As mensagens de erro podem ser confusas as vezes, atrapalhando, ao invés de auxiliar.				X	
H10: Help and documentation	Even though it is better if the system can be used without documentation, it may be necessary to provide help and documentation. Any such information should be easy to search, focused on the user's task, list concrete steps to be carried out, and not be too large.	Does the Textual DSL have a tutorial in order to provide the DSL's goal, the syntax usage and its meaning, as well as provide examples of the DSL's usage?	X		No site do projeto latex existe toda a documentação e livros para auxiliar.	X				
		Are all the commands included on the Textual DSL described in a clear way on the documentation support?	X							

Heuristic Evaluation Checklist for Textual DSL

This checklist is designed to be used together with the Process. The Nielsen Heuristics are used in the Heuristic Evaluation Checklist.

The following 0 to 4 rating scale can be used to rate the severity of usability problems:

Severity	Type	Description
0	Not applicable	I don't agree that this is a usability problem at all
1	Cosmetic problem only	need not be fixed unless extra time is available on project
2	Minor usability problem	fixing this should be given low priority
3	Major usability problem	important to fix, so should be given high priority
4	Usability catastrophe	imperative to fix this before product can be released

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Heuristic	Description	Question	Apply	Not apply	Description of each error occurrence	Severity (Check each of the problems found)				
						0	1	2	3	4
H1: Visibility of system status	The DSL should always keep users informed about what is going on, through appropriate feedback within reasonable time.	Does the Textual DSL provide immediate and adequate feedback on its status for each user action? For example, after an include or exclude task the language displays a commit message?			The compile does not shows where the modifications have being performed.		X			
		Do the elements available for the user specifically execute only one command? For example, the "undo" button only performs undo actions.					X			

H2: Match between language and the real world domain	The DSL must represent the user's language with words, phrases, and concepts familiar to the user instead of system-oriented. It should follow the conventions of the real world, making the information natural and logical.	Are the reserved keywords that compose the Textual DSL used on the user's real world domain? For example, a DSL developed for a domain related to libraries needs to have keywords related to the library domain.				X			
		Are the elements that compose the Textual DSL a good representation of the DSL's domain?				X			
		Do the elements that compose the Textual DSL meet the domain goal? The user understands the DSL goal by interacting with its elements.				X			
H3: User control and freedom	Users often choose DSL functions by mistake and will need a clearly marked "emergency exit" to leave the unwanted state without having to go through an extended dialogue. Support undo and redo.	Does the Textual DSL provide a mechanism in order to inform the restrictions of usage in case of, for example, mistyping or committing any kind of mistake?				X			
		Does the Textual DSL predict wrong decisions made by the users and warn them? For example, when the user clicks on a button for closing all the application and the tasks made by the user were not saved, does the Textual DSL warn the user that the application will be closed and nothing will be saved?			The problems are only showed after the .tex compilation	X			
H4: Consistency and standards	Users should not have to wonder whether different words, situations, or actions mean the same thing.	Are all the Textual elements apparently connected to each other? For example, are all the reserved keywords shown in the same color?				X			
		Are all the Textual elements connected to each other according to their names? For example, are all the				X			

		reserved keywords written in the same style, only using camelCase or only using underscores (_) to separate words?								
		In case of using abbreviations, are all the abbreviations consistent throughout the DSL usage?		X						
H5: Error prevention	Even better than good error messages is a careful design which prevents a problem from occurring in the first place. Either eliminate error-prone conditions or check for them and present users with a confirmation option before they commit to the action.(confirmation box)	Does the Textual DSL show confirmation boxes when the user performs actions considered dangerous (deleting things, etc)?			The DSL allows users to perform these actions without showing confirmation boxes.			X		
H6: Recognition rather than recall	Minimize the user's memory load by making objects, actions, and options visible. The user should not have to remember information from one part of the system to another. Instructions for use of the system should be visible or	Do reserved keywords have a meaningful and easy name so that the user can remember them in a fast way? In this case, keywords are words related to the domain of the textual DSL.				X				
		Are common tasks easy and fast to be executed? For example, opening a file or deleting an element.				X				

	easily retrievable whenever appropriate.									
H7: Flexibility and efficiency of use	Accelerators — unseen by the novice user — may often speed up the interaction for the expert user such that the language can cater to both inexperienced and experienced users. Allow users to tailor frequent actions.	Does the Textual DSL have shortcuts for expert users to make the usage of the DSL in a fast way? For example, providing short-cuts or functions to write basic code structures.					X			
		Does the Textual DSL provide all the elements in order to complete the desired task?					X			
		Are the Textual and Graphical DSLs structured in a coupled way? For example, if the user changes something on the Textual DSL, this change must be observed on the Graphical DSL and if the user changes something on the Visual DSL, this change must be observed on the Textual DSL.					X			
H8: Aesthetic and minimalist design	Dialogues should not contain information that is irrelevant or rarely needed. Every extra unit of information in a dialogue competes with the relevant units of information and diminishes their relative visibility.	In case of showing a dialog (when the user commits a mistake, for example), does this dialog show the possible reasons why the mistake was committed in a clear way?					X			
		In case of showing a dialog, does this dialog have the information shown in a short-text? The quantity of lines of a short text may vary according to the dialog and the information being exposed, but it is advised that a dialog does not have more than 3 lines of warning.		X						
		Is the Textual DSL composed by words easy to be seen on the screen					X			

		(with good-contrast color, easily identified by the end user)? For example, commands like "if/else" are shown in a different color from the rest of the code.								
H9: Help users recognize, diagnose, and recover from errors	Error messages should be expressed in plain language (no codes), precisely indicate the problem, and constructively suggest a solution.	In case of error, does the DSL show an appropriate error message where the user, after reading it, knows how to recover from the error or where to look for a solution?				X				
H10: Help and documentation	Even though it is better if the system can be used without documentation, it may be necessary to provide help and documentation. Any such information should be easy to search, focused on the user's task, list concrete steps to be carried out, and not be too large.	Does the Textual DSL have a tutorial in order to provide the DSL's goal, the syntax usage and its meaning, as well as provide examples of the DSL's usage?			The DSL itself does not have, however the templates have.		X			
		Are all the commands included on the Textual DSL described in a clear way on the documentation support?				X				

Heuristic Evaluation Checklist for Textual DSL

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Severity	Type	Description
0	Not applicable	I don't agree that this is a usability problem at all
1	Cosmetic problem only	need not be fixed unless extra time is available on project
2	Minor usability problem	fixing this should be given low priority
3	Major usability problem	important to fix, so should be given high priority
4	Usability catastrophe	imperative to fix this before product can be released

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Heuristic	Description	Question	Apply	Not apply	Description of each error occurrence	Severity (Check each of the problems found)				
						0	1	2	3	4
H1: Visibility of system status	The DSL should always keep users informed about what is going on, through appropriate feedback within reasonable time.	Does the Textual DSL provide immediate and adequate feedback on its status for each user action? For example, after an include or exclude task the language displays a commit message?		X	Não existe mensagem de commit de cada mudança, mas a DSL consegue informar em tempo real caso haja um erro menor (faltando um sinal de chaves por exemplo), antes de compilar.		x			
		Do the elements available for the user specifically execute only one command? For example, the "undo" button only performs undo actions.		X	Não existe necessariamente um botão para desfazer a ação realizada, isso é possível apenas através do menu de contexto do mouse ou das teclas de			x		

					atalho ctrl+z									
H2: Match between language and the real world domain	The DSL must represent the user's language with words, phrases, and concepts familiar to the user instead of system-oriented. It should follow the conventions of the real world, making the information natural and logical.	Are the reserved keywords that compose the Textual DSL used on the user's real world domain? For example, a DSL developed for a domain related to libraries needs to have keywords related to the library domain.	X											
		Are the elements that compose the Textual DSL a good representation of the DSL's domain?	X											
		Do the elements that compose the Textual DSL meet the domain goal? The user understands the DSL goal by interacting with its elements.	X											
H3: User control and freedom	Users often choose DSL functions by mistake and will need a clearly marked "emergency exit" to leave the unwanted state without having to go through an extended dialogue. Support undo and redo.	Does the Textual DSL provide a mechanism in order to inform the restrictions of usage in case of, for example, mistyping or committing any kind of mistake?	X											
		Does the Textual DSL predict wrong decisions made by the users and warn them? For example, when the user clicks on a button for closing all the application and the tasks made by the user were not saved, does the Textual DSL warn the user that the application will be closed and nothing will be saved?		X	No caso do exemplo não há aviso nenhum pois como é uma plataforma web, ocorre o salvamento automático. Contudo se há queda de internet o aviso de reconexão exibido pode não ser muito preciso. Falo isso pois já ocorreu de trabalhar em documento .tex nessa plataforma sem nenhum feedback de que a conexão havia caído (ou avisando que as mudanças realizadas offline poderiam ser perdidas). No momento em que ocorria a conexão todo o trabalho desenvolvido no período sem internet era perdido e o documento atualizado para a última "versão online".									X

H4: Consistency and standards	Users should not have to wonder whether different words, situations, or actions mean the same thing.	Are all the Textual elements apparently connected to each other? For example, are all the reserved keywords shown in the same color?	X							
		Are all the Textual elements connected to each other according to their names? For example, are all the reserved keywords written in the same style, only using camelCase or only using underscores (_) to separate words?	X							
		In case of using abbreviations, are all the abbreviations consistent throughout the DSL usage?	X							
H5: Error prevention	Even better than good error messages is a careful design which prevents a problem from occurring in the first place. Either eliminate error-prone conditions or check for them and present users with a confirmation option before they commit to the action.(confirmation box)	Does the Textual DSL show confirmation boxes when the user performs actions considered dangerous (deleting things, etc)?	X							
H6: Recognition rather than recall	Minimize the user's memory load by making objects, actions, and options visible. The	Do reserved keywords have a meaningful and easy name so that the user can remember them in a fast way? In this case, keywords are words related to the domain of the	X							

	user should not have to remember information from one part of the system to another. Instructions for use of the system should be visible or easily retrievable whenever appropriate.	textual DSL.								
		Are commons tasks easy and fast to be executed? For example, opening a file or deleting an element.	X							
H7: Flexibility and efficiency of use	Accelerators — unseen by the novice user — may often speed up the interaction for the expert user such that the language can cater to both inexperienced and experienced users. Allow users to tailor frequent actions.	Does the Textual DSL have shortcuts for expert users to make the usage of the DSL in a fast way? For example, providing short-cuts or functions to write basic code structures.	X							
		Does the Textual DSL provide all the elements in order to complete the desired task?	X							
		Are the Textual and Graphical DSLs structured in a coupled way? For example, if the user changes something on the Textual DSL, this change must be observed on the Graphical DSL and if the user changes something on the Visual DSL, this change must be observed on the Textual DSL.		X	Se considerar a DSL gráfica como a saída em PDF gerada pelo LaTeX, as mudanças ocorrem de fato. Contudo, às vezes pode não ser tão fácil percebê-las (principalmente as mudanças pequenas) em documentos maiores. Contudo é possível contornar isso até certo ponto com a função de histórico presente no menu superior direito.	X				
H8: Aesthetic and minimalist design	Dialogues should not contain information that is irrelevant or rarely needed. Every extra unit of information in a dialogue competes with the relevant	In case of showing a dialog (when the user commits a mistake, for example), does this dialog show the possible reasons why the mistake was committed in a clear way?	X							
		In case of showing a dialog, does this dialog have the information shown in a short-text? The quantity of lines of	X							

	units of information and diminishes their relative visibility.	a short text may vary according to the dialog and the information being exposed, but it is advised that a dialog does not have more than 3 lines of warning.								
		Is the Textual DSL composed by words easy to be seen on the screen (with good-contrast color, easily identified by the end user)? For example, commands like "if/else" are shown in a different color from the rest of the code.		X	No exemplo específico dado (comando if/else) não há diferença nas cores dos comandos quando é escrito alguma forma de algoritmo no .tex		X			
H9: Help users recognize, diagnose, and recover from errors	Error messages should be expressed in plain language (no codes), precisely indicate the problem, and constructively suggest a solution.	In case of error, does the DSL show an appropriate error message where the user, after reading it, knows how to recover from the error or where to look for a solution?		X	Não é sempre que as mensagens de erro são intuitiva ou fáceis de compreender. Muitas vezes é necessário inclusive um conhecimento muito mais técnico.					X
H10: Help and documentation	Even though it is better if the system can be used without documentation, it may be necessary to provide help and documentation. Any such information should be easy to search, focused on the user's task, list concrete steps to be carried out, and not be too large.	Does the Textual DSL have a tutorial in order to provide the DSL's goal, the syntax usage and its meaning, as well as provide examples of the DSL's usage?		X	Não tem tutorial nativo que ensine o básico durante a primeira utilização,					X
		Are all the commands included on the Textual DSL described in a clear way on the documentation support?	X							

Heuristic Evaluation CheckList for Textual DSL

This checklist is designed to be used together with the Process. The Nielsen Heuristics are used in the Heuristic Evaluation Checklist.

The following 0 to 4 rating scale can be used to rate the severity of usability problems:

Severity	Type	Description
0	Not applicable	I don't agree that this is a usability problem at all
1	Cosmetic problem only	need not be fixed unless extra time is available on project
2	Minor usability problem	fixing this should be given low priority
3	Major usability problem	important to fix, so should be given high priority
4	Usability catastrophe	imperative to fix this before product can be released

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Heuristic	Description	Question	Apply	Not apply	Description of each error occurrence	Severity (Check each of the problems found)				
						0	1	2	3	4
H1: Visibility of system status	The DSL should always keep users informed about what is going on, through appropriate feedback within reasonable time.	Does the Textual DSL provide immediate and adequate feedback on its status for each user action? For example, after an include or exclude task the language displays a commit message?	x							
		Do the elements available for the user specifically execute only one command? For example, the "undo" button only performs undo actions.	x							

H2: Match between language and the real world domain	The DSL must represent the user's language with words, phrases, and concepts familiar to the user instead of system-oriented. It should follow the conventions of the real world, making the information natural and logical.	Are the reserved keywords that compose the Textual DSL used on the user's real world domain? For example, a DSL developed for a domain related to libraries needs to have keywords related to the library domain.	x								
		Are the elements that compose the Textual DSL a good representation of the DSL's domain?	x								
		Do the elements that compose the Textual DSL meet the domain goal? The user understands the DSL goal by interacting with its elements.	x								
H3: User control and freedom	Users often choose DSL functions by mistake and will need a clearly marked "emergency exit" to leave the unwanted state without having to go through an extended dialogue. Support undo and redo.	Does the Textual DSL provide a mechanism in order to inform the restrictions of usage in case of, for example, mistyping or committing any kind of mistake?	x								
		Does the Textual DSL predict wrong decisions made by the users and warn them? For example, when the user clicks on a button for closing all the application and the tasks made by the user were not saved, does the Textual DSL warn the user that the application will be closed and nothing will be saved?	x								
H4: Consistency and standards	Users should not have to wonder whether different words, situations, or actions mean the same thing.	Are all the Textual elements apparently connected to each other? For example, are all the reserved keywords shown in the same color?	x								
		Are all the Textual elements connected to each other according to their names? For example, are all the	x								

		reserved keywords written in the same style, only using camelCase or only using underscores (_) to separate words?								
		In case of using abbreviations, are all the abbreviations consistent throughout the DSL usage?	x							
H5: Error prevention	Even better than good error messages is a careful design which prevents a problem from occurring in the first place. Either eliminate error-prone conditions or check for them and present users with a confirmation option before they commit to the action.(confirmation box)	Does the Textual DSL show confirmation boxes when the user performs actions considered dangerous (deleting things, etc)?		x	Apresenta em alguns casos específicos, como quando vai mudar uma imagem por outra. Mas não é muito grave, pois não existem muitas ações perigosas na DSL.		x			
H6: Recognition rather than recall	Minimize the user's memory load by making objects, actions, and options visible. The user should not have to remember information from one part of the system to another. Instructions for use of the system should be visible or	Do reserved keywords have a meaningful and easy name so that the user can remember them in a fast way? In this case, keywords are words related to the domain of the textual DSL.	x							
		Are commons tasks easy and fast to be executed? For example, opening a file or deleting an element.	x							

	easily retrievable whenever appropriate.									
H7: Flexibility and efficiency of use	Accelerators — unseen by the novice user — may often speed up the interaction for the expert user such that the language can cater to both inexperienced and experienced users. Allow users to tailor frequent actions.	Does the Textual DSL have shortcuts for expert users to make the usage of the DSL in a fast way? For example, providing short-cuts or functions to write basic code structures.	x							
		Does the Textual DSL provide all the elements in order to complete the desired task?	x							
		Are the Textual and Graphical DSLs structured in a coupled way? For example, if the user changes something on the Textual DSL, this change must be observed on the Graphical DSL and if the user changes something on the Visual DSL, this change must be observed on the Textual DSL.		x	Não existe uma DSL gráfica, apenas uma previsão de como o pdf gerado vai ficar.	x				
H8: Aesthetic and minimalist design	Dialogues should not contain information that is irrelevant or rarely needed. Every extra unit of information in a dialogue competes with the relevant units of information and diminishes their relative visibility.	In case of showing a dialog (when the user commits a mistake, for example), does this dialog show the possible reasons why the mistake was committed in a clear way?	x							
		In case of showing a dialog, does this dialog have the information shown in a short-text? The quantity of lines of a short text may vary according to the dialog and the information being exposed, but it is advised that a dialog does not have more than 3 lines of warning.	x							
		Is the Textual DSL composed by words easy to be seen on the screen	x							

		(with good-contrast color, easily identified by the end user)? For example, commands like “if/else” are shown in a different color from the rest of the code.								
H9: Help users recognize, diagnose, and recover from errors	Error messages should be expressed in plain language (no codes), precisely indicate the problem, and constructively suggest a solution.	In case of error, does the DSL show an appropriate error message where the user, after reading it, knows how to recover from the error or where to look for a solution?		x	Alguns erros estão misturados com códigos, o que faz com que seja difícil identificar rapidamente com qual erro estamos lidando.				x	
H10: Help and documentation	Even though it is better if the system can be used without documentation, it may be necessary to provide help and documentation. Any such information should be easy to search, focused on the user's task, list concrete steps to be carried out, and not be too large.	Does the Textual DSL have a tutorial in order to provide the DSL's goal, the syntax usage and its meaning, as well as provide examples of the DSL's usage?	x							
		Are all the commands included on the Textual DSL described in a clear way on the documentation support?	x							

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4	Usability catastrophe	imperative to fix this before product can be released

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Heuristic	Description	Question	Apply	Not apply	Description of each error occurrence	Severity (Check each of the problems found)				
						0	1	2	3	4
H1: Visibility of system status	The DSL should always keep users informed about what is going on, through appropriate feedback within reasonable time.	Does the Textual DSL provide immediate and adequate feedback on its status for each user action? For example, after an include or exclude task the language displays a commit message?	x			x				
		Do the elements available for the user specifically execute only one command? For example, the "undo" button only performs undo actions.		x	Don't exists undo button			x		

		reserved keywords written in the same style, only using camelCase or only using underscores (_) to separate words?								
		In case of using abbreviations, are all the abbreviations consistent throughout the DSL usage?	x			x				
H5: Error prevention	Even better than good error messages is a careful design which prevents a problem from occurring in the first place. Either eliminate error-prone conditions or check for them and present users with a confirmation option before they commit to the action.(confirmation box)	Does the Textual DSL show confirmation boxes when the user performs actions considered dangerous (deleting things, etc)?		x	Apresenta apenas em alguns casos (sobrescrita de imagens).		x			
H6: Recognition rather than recall	Minimize the user's memory load by making objects, actions, and options visible. The user should not have to remember information from one part of the system to another. Instructions for use of the system should be visible or	Do reserved keywords have a meaningful and easy name so that the user can remember them in a fast way? In this case, keywords are words related to the domain of the textual DSL.	x				x			
		Are commons tasks easy and fast to be executed? For example, opening a file or deleting an element.	x				x			

	easily retrievable whenever appropriate.									
H7: Flexibility and efficiency of use	Accelerators — unseen by the novice user — may often speed up the interaction for the expert user such that the language can cater to both inexperienced and experienced users. Allow users to tailor frequent actions.	Does the Textual DSL have shortcuts for expert users to make the usage of the DSL in a fast way? For example, providing short-cuts or functions to write basic code structures.	x				x			
		Does the Textual DSL provide all the elements in order to complete the desired task?	x				x			
		Are the Textual and Graphical DSLs structured in a coupled way? For example, if the user changes something on the Textual DSL, this change must be observed on the Graphical DSL and if the user changes something on the Visual DSL, this change must be observed on the Textual DSL.		x	Apenas após a ação “compilar”			x		
H8: Aesthetic and minimalist design	Dialogues should not contain information that is irrelevant or rarely needed. Every extra unit of information in a dialogue competes with the relevant units of information and diminishes their relative visibility.	In case of showing a dialog (when the user commits a mistake, for example), does this dialog show the possible reasons why the mistake was committed in a clear way?	x				x			
		In case of showing a dialog, does this dialog have the information shown in a short-text? The quantity of lines of a short text may vary according to the dialog and the information being exposed, but it is advised that a dialog does not have more than 3 lines of warning.	x				x			
		Is the Textual DSL composed by words easy to be seen on the screen	x				x			

		(with good-contrast color, easily identified by the end user)? For example, commands like "if/else" are shown in a different color from the rest of the code.								
H9: Help users recognize, diagnose, and recover from errors	Error messages should be expressed in plain language (no codes), precisely indicate the problem, and constructively suggest a solution.	In case of error, does the DSL show an appropriate error message where the user, after reading it, knows how to recover from the error or where to look for a solution?	x				x			
H10: Help and documentation	Even though it is better if the system can be used without documentation, it may be necessary to provide help and documentation. Any such information should be easy to search, focused on the user's task, list concrete steps to be carried out, and not be too large.	Does the Textual DSL have a tutorial in order to provide the DSL's goal, the syntax usage and its meaning, as well as provide examples of the DSL's usage?	x		I don't know a tutorial of the LateX in overleaf.		x			
		Are all the commands included on the Textual DSL described in a clear way on the documentation support?	x				x			

